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“MA'AM? MOM?”

Another morning, another rush of pace,
Leaving with bags packed, to my children a warm embrace.
Off to school where Mom becomes Ma'am,
Mind's set to teach, my heart goes warm.

Jumping from class to class, I nourish and discuss,
My pride is in these students who strive hard to pass.
Yet in my heart, a single thought lingers,
My little ones, so eager to explore the world's wonders.

Deadlines, class reports, and lessons so many,
Can't wait to head back where love flows plenty.
Tiny voices that make my insides flutter,
They see me and say, "Mom, you're here!"

A mom and teacher: two roles in one,
I give my best to end the day and say, "Well done."
Balancing both may feel like a fight,
Yet love makes every struggle right.